

GRAMMATICAL COMPETENCE AND SPEAKING SKILLS

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Grammatical Competence and Speaking Skills

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Abstract

This study investigates the relationship between grammatical competence and speaking skills among Grade XII students at Guinacot National High School in Guindulman, Bohol, during the 2017-2018 academic year. Specifically, it examines students' proficiency in subject-verb agreement, verb tenses, modifiers, and prepositions, alongside their speaking abilities in fluency, content, vocal, and physical expression. Employing a descriptive-correlational design, the research assesses whether a significant relationship exists between students' grammatical competence and their ability to speak effectively. Findings revealed that the majority of students exhibited emerging competence in subject-verb agreement, while they demonstrated approaching competence in verb tenses and modifiers. Their overall grammatical performance was below expected proficiency levels. Similarly, speaking skills were predominantly rated at the emerging competence level across fluency, content, and expressions. The study's statistical analysis confirmed a significant positive correlation between grammatical competence and speaking skills, suggesting that mastery of grammar substantially impacts students' oral communication abilities. Based on these findings, the study proposes an action plan to improve the teaching of grammar and speaking skills, emphasizing the need for early intervention, reinforcement of grammar lessons, and confidence-building activities in speaking. The study concludes that a strong foundation in grammatical competence is critical for enhancing students' speaking abilities and recommends targeted teaching strategies to support these competencies from grade school to senior high school.

Keywords: *grammatical competence, oral communication, speaking skills, subject-verb agreement, and verb tenses*

Introduction

Communication plays a pivotal role in the exchange of information, ideas, and emotions, encompassing a variety of forms such as spoken words, sounds, signs, and behaviors. It serves essential functions, including regulation, social interaction, motivation, information sharing, and emotional expression. As highlighted by Flores (2016), these functions enable individuals to influence behavior, engage socially, persuade others, share data, and appeal to emotions, ultimately achieving the primary goal of communication—shared meaning.

The effectiveness of communication is often linked to the communicator's ability to convey clear messages. According to Tapang (2012), communication goals can be categorized into three types: self-presentation (how one wants to be perceived), relational (how relationships are developed and maintained), and instrumental (how one achieves specific objectives through manipulation or persuasion). Mastery of these goals contributes to effective communication, which relies not only on verbal clarity but also on nonverbal cues, active listening, and emotional intelligence. However, a significant factor that affects communication competency is grammatical proficiency. Poor grammatical skills can undermine one's ability to communicate effectively, which is a prevalent issue among students.

In recent years, several studies have highlighted a concerning decline in English communication skills among Filipino students and professionals. National Achievement Test (NAT) results have consistently shown low proficiency in English across various academic years, particularly at Guinacot National High School, where English scores ranged from 45.10% to 61.51% between 2011 and 2015. The researcher, a seasoned English teacher, has observed similar trends in the classroom, with students showing little appreciation for the importance of grammar, leading to deficiencies in their speaking abilities. This growing concern has motivated the researcher to investigate and design interventions aimed at improving students' grammatical competence and speaking skills.

This study seeks to address the relationship between grammatical competence and speaking ability, using Canale and Swain's (1980) theory of communicative competence as its theoretical foundation. According to the theorists, communicative competence comprises four components: grammatical competence, discourse competence, sociolinguistic competence, and strategic competence. Grammatical competence involves knowledge of vocabulary, sentence formation, and the ability to construct clear, meaningful sentences. This study focuses on how mastering grammar contributes to improved speaking skills, an area that remains crucial for students' academic and professional success.

The current research builds upon previous studies that have documented the decline in students' grammatical and communication abilities. For example, studies by Mellejor (1983) and Bautista (1989) revealed students' lack of mastery in grammar, particularly in subject-verb agreement and sentence structure. Similarly, Espina (2002) and Buscano (2006) found a consistent deterioration in communication competencies across different levels of education. By examining these issues, this study aims to determine the extent to which grammatical competence influences speaking ability and to develop strategies for enhancing both skills in students.

Ultimately, this research aims to provide insights and practical solutions to address the grammatical and communicative deficiencies

observed among students. The findings will guide the development of targeted interventions and learning plans to help students improve their grammatical competence and speaking ability, thus equipping them with the skills needed for effective communication in both academic and real-world settings.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the grammatical competence and its possible relationship with the speaking ability of Grade XII students of Guinacot National High School in Guindulman, Bohol for the Academic Year 2017-2018. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the grammatical competence of the students in terms of:
 - 1.1. subject- verb agreement;
 - 1.2. verb tenses;
 - 1.3. use of modifiers; and
 - 1.4. use of prepositions?
2. What is the level of the speaking skill of students in terms of:
 - 2.1. fluency;
 - 2.2. content;
 - 2.3. vocal expression; and
 - 2.4. physical expression?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the students' grammatical competence and their speaking skill?
4. What action pal could be proposed to improve the teaching of grammar and speaking of the students in the basic education?

Methodology

Research Design

This study made use of descriptive-correlational design. It describes the grammatical competence of the respondents in terms of subject-verb agreement, verb-tenses, use of modifier and use of preposition. It also sought to describe the level of respondents' speaking skill in terms of fluency, content, vocal expression and physical expression. It also determines whether a positive correlation exists between grammatical competence and speaking skill.

Respondents

The respondents of the study were all Grade XII students of Guinacot National High School in Guindulman, Bohol for School Year 2017-2018. These students were clustered into five sections, namely GAS 1, GAS 2, TVL- ICT, TVL- Caregiving and TVL- Hairdressing. The students who are in GAS 1 and GAS 2 are taking up the General Academic Strand leading to Engineering courses for GAS 1 and leading to Business, Accountancy and other related courses for GAS 2. The students in the three TVL sections are taking up the Technical, Vocational and Livelihood Track leading to a career in ICT, Caregiving and Hairdressing Beauty Care respectively. Thirty percent of the total population were tapped as the respondents. The researcher chose the Grade XII students because they were the first batch of students under the K-12 curriculum of the Department of Education. Based on the results, researcher made an action plan for the students which may help them improve their grammatical and oral communication skills.

Table 1. Distribution of Respondents

<i>Grade XII Sections</i>	<i>Total Number of Students</i>	<i>Sample Population</i>
GAS 1	40	12
GAS 2	41	12
TVL - ICT	34	10
TVL - Caregiving	31	9
TVL - Hairdressing	27	9
Total	173	52

Instrument

The researcher utilized a two-part questionnaire. Part I was the Grammatical Competence Test, which focused on key aspects of syntax, specifically subject-verb agreement, tenses of verbs, use of modifiers, and use of prepositions. Each of the four categories contained ten items, for a total of 40 items, with the highest possible score being 40. This part of the test was adapted from Tapang (2012), providing a reliable framework for assessing grammatical competence. Part II was the Speaking Ability Test, in which respondents were required to answer the question, "What is the importance of studying English?" orally. Each respondent was given up to three minutes to respond, and their performance was evaluated based on fluency, content, and vocal and physical expressions, with a maximum possible score of 20. To ensure the reliability and validity of the research instrument, a pilot test was conducted with a sample group of students who shared similar characteristics with the study's respondents. Feedback from this pilot test was used to refine both the Grammatical Competence and Speaking Ability Tests, ensuring the clarity and appropriateness of the instrument for the target population.

Procedure

The research process commenced with obtaining the necessary approvals from the Division of Bohol Superintendent and the school principal of Guinacot National High School. Following this, coordination with Grade XII advisers took place to schedule and discuss the administration of the tests.

The test questionnaires were distributed to students in a classroom setting, where they were allotted one hour to complete the test. Afterward, the answer sheets were collected and scored using a pre-prepared answer key.

For the speaking ability test, respondents were oriented in a separate room. The question, "What is the importance of studying English?" was posed individually to each student by a panel of three raters, who assessed their performance using a scoring rubric. The raters, all qualified educators with relevant experience, evaluated the respondents based on fluency, content, and vocal and physical expressions.

Data Analysis

The respondents' individual raw scores on syntax, particularly in subject-verb agreement, verb tenses, use of modifiers and the use of prepositions were tabulated. Simple frequency counts were done and percentages were obtained. The scores were categorized according to descriptors denoting level of skills or competence: competent, approaching, developing, emerging and beginning. Result in the speaking ability test utilized the same descriptive scale. The Pearson Coefficient of Correlation was used to determine the relationship between grammatical competence and speaking skill.

Ethical Considerations

This study adhered to ethical standards by securing informed consent from all participants, ensuring their confidentiality, and maintaining voluntary participation without any coercion. No harm came to participants, and the research received ethics committee approval. The researcher declared no conflicts of interest and reported findings transparently and honestly. Cultural sensitivity was respected throughout the research process.

Results and Discussion

This section includes the presentation, analysis and interpretation of data. The first part describes the grammatical competence of Grade XII students. The second part presents the respondents' discourse competence. The last part deals with the correlation between the students' grammatical and discourse competence.

The respondents' grammatical competence was measured through their knowledge on subject-verb agreement, verb tenses, use of modifiers and use of prepositions.

Table 2 Respondents' Grammatical Competence

Competence Level	Subject - Verb Agreement		Verb Tenses		Use of Modifiers		Use of Prepositions	
	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
Component	0	0	7	13.5	16	30.8	1	1.9
Approaching Competence	7	13.5	19	36.5	18	34.6	16	30.8
Developing Competence	11	21.2	21	40.4	11	21.2	21	40.4
Emerging Competence	24	46.2	5	9.6	7	13.5	13	25.0
Beginning Competence	10	19.2	0	0	0	0	1	1.9
Total	52	100.0	52	100.0	52	100.0	52	100.0

Table 2 shows the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents based on the result of the grammatical competence test. On subject-verb agreement, 24 of the 52 respondents or 46.2 percent have emerging competence only. It means that they were able to answer correctly 2-3 questions out of 10 items. There was no respondent who is in the competent level in terms of subject-verb agreement. The result suggests that the students do not have yet the competence in the subject-verb agreement. The results also suggest that the respondents have not mastered yet the rules on subject-verb agreement. In terms of verb tenses, 21 of the 52 respondents have developing competence. It means that they correctly answered only 4-5 questions out of 10 items. The data suggest the respondents have not really learned the concept about verb tenses. They do not know what form of the verb to use to indicate the specific time element. There were seven respondents who are in the competent level in terms of verb tenses.

On the use of modifiers, there were 18 of the 52 or 34.6 percent of the respondents who are in the approaching competence level. It

means that they correctly answered 6-7 questions out of 10 items. The results suggest that compared to other areas, the respondents have gained a certain degree of mastery on the use of modifiers. There were 16 respondents who are in the competent level in terms of the use of modifiers. The results imply that the respondents possess a good background in the use of modifiers.

Lastly, on the use of prepositions, 21 of the 52 or 40.4 percent of the respondents have developing competence. It means that 4-5 questions out of the 10 items were correctly answered. There was only one respondent who is in the competent level in the use of prepositions. The results indicate that most of the respondents do not have good foundation knowledge and use on prepositions. Moreover, the result also suggests that the lessons in grammar like subject-verb agreement, verb tenses, use of modifiers and the use of prepositions should be taught properly to the learners starting from the grade school level, it is because the learners really need a strong or good grammatical foundation in English. The results also show that the respondents do not have the required mastery in English proficiency.

Table 3. *Overall Grammatical Competence of the Respondents*

Grammatical Aspect	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
Subject-Verb Agreement	2.29	Emerging Competence
Verb Tenses	3.54	Approaching Competence
Use of Modifiers	3.83	Approaching Competence
Use of Prepositions	3.06	Developing Competence

Table 3 reveals how the Grade XII students fared in terms of grammatical competence. In the subject-verb agreement, the participants have emerging competence only. The result suggests that students have not mastered the rules on the agreement of the verb and the number of the subject. The result is alarming because lessons on subject-verb agreement are supposed to be learned in the elementary and junior high school. However, the results indicate that these students have not gained mastery of the lessons and that they have difficulty in identifying correct form of the verb in relation to the number of the subject.

In terms of verb tenses and use of modifiers, the participants have approaching competence only. The results suggest that students have not also mastered the use of correct tenses of the verb and the correct usage of modifiers. The result is also alarming since functional skills should have been learned already in the grade school.

On the use of prepositions, results indicate that the research participants have developing competence only. The results suggest that students do not have mastery on the correct usage of prepositions. The result is also alarming because lessons on prepositions were already given to them when they were still in grade school.

Of the four grammatical aspects which were tested in this research, it is in the verb tenses and use of modifiers where the research participants have approaching competence. It is a good indication that this group of students has at least acquired appropriate knowledge in verb tenses and the use of modifiers. The previous studies which the researcher mentioned in the theoretical background that relates to the findings of this research were the studies of Mellejor (1983), Bautista (1989) and Maniwang (2004). The findings about the respondents' weakness in subject-verb agreement is in agreement with the findings in the study of Bautista (1989). The findings about the weakness in Grammar of the respondents agree with the findings of the study of Mellejor (1983) and Maniwang (2004).

Table 4. *Speaking Skills of the Respondents*

Competence Level	Fluency		Content		Vocal Expression		Physical Expression	
	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
Component	1	1.9	0	0	1	1.9	1	1.9
Approaching Competence	6	11.5	7	13.5	6	11.5	7	13.5
Developing Competence	15	28.8	21	40.4	17	32.7	14	26.9
Emerging Competence	21	40.4	20	38.5	21	40.4	22	42.3
Beginning Competence	9	17.3	4	7.7	7	13.5	8	15.4
Total	52	100.0	52	100.0	52	100.0	52	100.0

Table 4 shows the respondents' speaking skills. On fluency, 21 of the 52 respondents or 40.4 percent have emerging competence. It means that they only scored 2 points out of the maximum of 5 points. There was only one respondent who is in the competent level in fluency. The result suggests that most of the respondents are not fluent in speaking.

In terms of content, 21 of the 52 respondents have developing competence. It means that they scored only three points out of the maximum of five points in content. There is no respondent who is in the competent level in terms of content. The result of the speaking ability test is really consistent with the results of the study of Sarabosing (1997) which states that the respondents were not competent in speaking.

For vocal expression, there were 21 of the 52 respondents who are in the emerging competence level. It means that they got only 2 out of the maximum of 5 in terms of vocal expression. There was no respondent who is classified as competent in terms of vocal expression. With this result, it can be said that the respondents have no good background about vocal expression. Lastly, in physical expression, 22 out of 52 respondents emerging competence. It means that they got only 2 out of 5 in terms of physical expression. There is only one respondent who is in the competent level in terms of physical expression. The researcher found out that most of the respondents are not having good foundation in the use of physical expression which includes gestures, confidence, presence and among others.

The results of the speaking ability test of the respondents suggest that the respondents do not possess competence in speaking. Moreover, the researcher realized that the teaching of speaking should be taught properly to the learners starting from the grade school level, it is because the learners really need a strong or good foundation on the different speaking or oral communication lessons.

Table 5. *Summary of the Speaking Skills of the Respondents*

Speaking Aspect	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
Fluency	2.40	Emerging Competence
Content	2.60	Emerging Competence
Vocal Expression	2.48	Emerging Competence
Physical Expression	2.44	Emerging Competence

Table 5 presents the summary of the speaking skill of the Grade XII students in terms of fluency, content, vocal expression and physical expression. The respondents are all in the emerging competence. The result means that they got a score of 2 only in the speaking ability test with the highest score of 5. The weighted mean for fluency is 2.40, for content is 2.60, for vocal expression is 2.48 and for physical expression is 2.44. All the weighted means fall under the emerging competence only. The results mean that the respondents are having the difficulty when it comes to speaking. The result indicates that the respondents do not have a good communication skill. The results of the speaking ability test are the same with the findings in the study of Sarabosing (1997), which states that the respondents were not competent with the language as they ought to be. Moreover, the researcher also realized that learners should be taught properly on the different lessons about speaking or oral communication, it is because oral communication skill is very important for the learners.

Table 6. *Relationship Between Students' Grammatical Competence and Speaking Skills*

Variables	Mean	Std. Deviation	R-value	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Grammatical Competence	19.3462	5.53734	0.714	0.000	Very High Correlation (Significant)	Reject Ho

Table 6 shows the relationship between grammatical competence and speaking skills of the respondents. The computed r value is 0.714 which is greater than the p value of 0.000 which means that it has really a very high correlation or significant relationship.

In this research, the null hypothesis that "grammatical competence of students does not affect their speaking ability has to be rejected to indicate that grammatical competence of students greatly influences their speaking skills. The findings of the study means that grammatical competence of an individual is really affecting his/her speaking ability. When one is good at grammar, he/she is good in speaking also. Grammatical competence is really required in speaking. Good content cannot be presented well in speaking if the speaker has low grammatical competence. The findings suggest that competence in grammar really affect the respondents' speaking skill. It is really difficult for an individual to express his or her ideas if he or she finds grammar rules difficult.

Conclusions

The findings of this study demonstrate that students' grammatical competence significantly influences their speaking skills. A strong foundation in grammar is essential for effective communication, as individuals with limited grammatical knowledge often struggle to express their ideas clearly. This highlights the critical role that grammar instruction plays in developing students' speaking abilities.

The results suggest that enhancing grammatical instruction in educational settings could improve students' overall communication skills, particularly in oral expression. Therefore, educators should prioritize integrating comprehensive grammar lessons into language curricula to foster both grammatical competence and speaking proficiency, which are crucial for students' success in real-world communication.

The researcher presents the following recommendations to enhance the teaching of grammatical competence and speaking skills:

Reinforcement of Grammar Lessons:

Students should be exposed to authentic tasks that require the practical application of grammar, such as writing projects, role-playing activities, and collaborative tasks.

Regular grammar drills and exercises should be provided to facilitate better internalization and mastery. These could be further enhanced through digital platforms offering interactive grammar games or quizzes.

Grammar rules, particularly subject-verb agreement, should be emphasized using a mix of traditional and modern teaching tools, such as interactive whiteboards, educational apps, and video tutorials that provide visual and auditory reinforcement.

Early Development of Speaking Skills.

Speaking skills should be systematically developed from grade school to build a solid foundation. This can be achieved by incorporating speaking practice into daily lessons through debate sessions, presentations, and group discussions. Innovative techniques such as integrating speech recognition software and virtual reality (VR) environments can provide students with more engaging, real-life speaking experiences.

Adoption of the Proposed Action Plan.

The researcher's proposed action plan, which includes strategies for improving both grammatical competence and speaking skills, is recommended for adoption. The plan encourages the use of a blended learning approach, combining traditional teaching methods with technology-driven tools, such as language learning apps and online grammar resources.

Confidence Building in Speaking.

Activities that promote confidence in speaking should be incorporated into the curriculum. These may include public speaking workshops, peer-to-peer conversations, and interactive storytelling. Gamified platforms like speech simulators could also be introduced to allow students to practice speaking in a low-pressure, supportive environment.

Expansion of Future Research.

Future studies could replicate this research by exploring other aspects of grammar, such as pronoun-antecedent agreement, order of adjectives, and conjunctions, in addition to subject-verb agreement, verb tenses, use of modifiers, and prepositions. Furthermore, longitudinal studies could be conducted to assess the long-term impact of technology-integrated grammar and speaking lessons.

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